

HANDWRITTEN TEXT RECOGNITION APPLIED ON BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE TOOLS

SARA EL HABBARI *

LAMSAD, Hassan First University-Settat, National School of Applied Sciences, Berrechid, Morocco.

*Corresponding Author Email: elhabbarisara@gmail.com

M'HAMED-AMINE SOUMIAA

LAMSAD, Hassan First University-Settat, National School of Applied Sciences, Berrechid, Morocco.

Email: medamine17@hotmail.com

MOHAMED MANSOURI

LAMSAD, Hassan First University-Settat, National School of Applied Sciences, Berrechid, Morocco.

Email: mansouri1969@yahoo.fr

Abstract

Carried by the wave of digitalization, companies are increasingly relying on the use of digitized documents, hence the necessity for high-performing handwriting recognition systems. Currently, artificial intelligence effectively fulfills this need through its text recognition and conversion techniques such as HTR (Handwritten Text Recognition), specifically tailored for handwritten texts. Unlike other IT domains, such as business intelligence, which still encounter difficulties in this area—specifically when it comes to extracting available data from scanned, handwritten documents in one or multiple languages. In this work, we utilized the HTR technique to address the challenge of extracting data from scanned handwritten forms into a BI tool, aiming to create a dashboard within this tool based on the data transcribed by the HTR.

Keywords: HTR, BI, IA, OCR, Text Recognition, Handprint, AWS, Python, Deep Learning, Artificial Neural Network.

1. INTRODUCTION

Every day, companies collect, process, and store a significant amount of data related to their activities. These data can come from multiple sources, have heterogeneous formats, include a large volume of information, and differ in granularity levels. For these reasons and many others, managing this data can prove complex and present a real challenge to companies, both technically and functionally. To tackle this situation, organizations are increasingly turning to Business Intelligence (BI): a set of IT solutions that consolidate, model, and present important data in summary form for effective monitoring of business activities and strategic decision-making.

Despite the technical advancements BI tools have seen so far, they still struggle to effectively manage all data sources, particularly scanned files. This stands in contrast to the digitalization policies adopted by most companies today, relying on digital document formats to facilitate storage, indexing, classification, and archiving. Scanned documents essentially present static images that BI tools struggle to thoroughly analyze to extract text and embedded data. Moreover, the nature of scanned text, whether typed on a computer or handwritten in one or multiple languages, further complicates the data extraction process for these tools.

This issue isn't just limited to BI; it has also challenged Artificial Intelligence (AI) for years due to the multitude and complexity of required operations, such as classification, segmentation, character and object recognition, learning, and more.

Today, following various research efforts, the topic of data extraction from scanned files is being addressed more or less effectively by deep learning algorithms within AI and its text and object recognition techniques, including:

- **OCR** (Optical Character Recognition)
- **HTR** (Handwritten Text Recognition)
- **ICR** (Intelligent Character Recognition)
- **IWR** (Intelligent Word Recognition)

In a previous article [1], we used OCRs to propose a solution for extracting data from scanned PDFs and images into a BI tool. With this solution, we managed to retrieve data from a form filled on a computer and subsequently scanned into a BI tool, something the tool couldn't natively accomplish through its PDF connector.

However, the OCR technique proved limited when dealing with forms manually filled in using one or multiple languages.

Through this article, we'll focus on handwritten formats within scanned files and propose a new solution combining the technical capabilities of a BI tool with advanced AI programs. The aim is to leverage data from these files for activity monitoring dashboards created by BI tools.

For a better understanding of our work, we will break down this manuscript into five parts:

In the first part, we will demonstrate the incapacity of an OCR to read information from a handwritten and scanned PDF file before proposing a new solution to address this issue.

During the second part, we will define the artificial intelligence methods that we have adopted in the context of this study.

Next, in the third part, we will provide a detailed presentation of the implemented solution. This includes the dataset and BI tool chosen for the demonstration, the installations and configurations made, the Python programs developed, the integration process of these programs into the BI tool, and the obtained results. Following that, we will compare and qualify the accuracy of these results in the fourth part.

Finally, we will conclude by synthesizing the advantages and disadvantages of the proposed solution.

2. OCR's LIMITATIONS

OCR, or Optical Character Recognition, encompasses all methods and solutions enabling the automatic identification and extraction of text from images and printed or scanned documents.

Over the years, OCR systems have improved in accuracy due to integrated artificial intelligence technologies, but they still have limitations due to several factors that can make the recognition process challenging, such as [2]:

- Document quality: Documents that have been photocopied multiple times, contain folds, or were generated with insufficient resolution can lead to recognition errors.
- Printing: The type of printer used can also degrade document quality and complicate the recognition task; for instance, an inkjet printer might introduce smudges and spread characters.
- Variability in shapes: Depending on the language and font used, characters can vary in appearance. Therefore, identifying them using OCR can be difficult or even impossible.
- Handwriting: Recognizing handwritten text is a delicate task that OCRs have struggled with until now because writing styles vary significantly from one person to another.

The challenges posed by handwritten optical character recognition are more complex than those related to printed writing. This was confirmed when attempting to apply the OCR system we developed, as detailed in a previous article [1], to a handwritten and scanned form in order to utilize its data in a BI tool.

The OCR we implemented utilizes Python's Pytesseract library, based on the open-source text recognition engine Tesseract. Figures 1 and 2 respectively show the results obtained when applying it to the same form in printed and handwritten versions.

Figure 1: Result of data extraction from the printed form

Figure 2: Result of data extraction from the handwritten form

As seen in Figure 2, the data from the handwritten form was not detected by Tesseract, unlike the printed form. This observation led us to seek a new solution better suited for extracting handwritten data from scanned documents.

The solution we found relies on using a method of automatic text recognition called HTR (Handwritten Text Recognition), which we will explain in detail in the next chapter.

3. HANDWRITTEN TEXT RECOGNITION

As we explained in the previous chapter, standard OCR systems struggle, if not entirely fail, to convert handwritten text, despite being available since the 1970s. However, the application of deep learning methods, particularly neural networks, can yield significantly better results than OCRs. In the following sections, we'll delve into the detailed concepts related to the recognition method we utilized in this work: Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR).

3.1 Deep Learning

Deep learning, a subset of artificial intelligence, mimics human brain behavior in terms of learning and data categorization [3]. It employs a specific architecture of artificial neural networks consisting of three or more layers with interconnected nodes, as depicted in Figure 3 below [4]:

Figure 3: Architecture of an artificial neural network

Each layer receives input data, processes it, and passes it to the next layer. This sequential processing refines recognition, classification, and object categorization from one layer to another, resulting in a precise description of objects present in the input data.

3.2 Deep learning applied to image recognition

Image recognition is one of the most significant and critical applications of deep learning. Through its multiple layers, deep learning can extract relevant features from a sample of images, gradually learn about these features through each layer, and return identified characteristics in new images.

The general process of image recognition involves two main phases, as illustrated in Figure 4 [5]:

- **Training phase:** This phase aims to train the model based on a significant volume of previously labeled and classified images, enabling it to learn and recognize a specific object or entity.
- **Testing phase:** This phase tests the model's predictions against real-world data. It involves predicting labels for test data based on the previously trained model.

Figure 4: Standard process of image recognition through deep learning

Through this process, we can recognize text present in images and scanned documents, which is the objective of this work. Specifically, we can identify handwritten text in these documents, despite its increased difficulty due to variations in individual writing styles.

3.3 Handwriting text recognition

Handwriting text recognition is the process of converting handwritten text on an electronic medium or captured in a static image into digitally encoded text. There are two types of handwriting recognition [6]:

- **Offline recognition:** Extracts text from an image, such as a scanned document.
- **Online recognition:** Interprets the trajectory of written text using specific hardware like digital pens, styli on electronic agendas, or touchscreen tablets/PCs. This method is more precise as it detects writing order, shape, direction, and position in real-time.

In the following sections, we'll focus on offline format, represented by the process in Figure 5 [4]:

Figure 5: Standard process of offline image recognition

- **Image Pre-processing:** Enhances image quality, locates relevant areas, and prepares it for subsequent processing.
- **Segmentation:** Isolates textual elements (words and characters) for recognition.
- **Feature extraction:** Extracts distinguishing characteristics of characters and describes shapes belonging to the same class distinctly.
- **Classification:** Determines the input object's class based on previously extracted features.

Several deep learning algorithms are used for handwriting recognition [7]:

- Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)
- Semi-Incremental Recognition Method
- Incremental Recognition Method
- Line and Word Segmentation
- Part-Based Method
- Slope and Slant Correction Method
- Ensemble Method
- Zoning Method
- Comparison of Different Methods

Each algorithm has its specificities and applications. However, CNN boasts the highest level of accuracy among the eight methods listed above and is therefore often used for handwriting recognition, especially for handwritten text.

The solution we will present in the next chapter utilizes Amazon's deep learning services for extracting handwritten data from scanned documents.

4. METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, we will detail the working methodology we followed to extract handwritten data from a sample of scanned forms, aiming to use them on a BI dashboard. First, we'll introduce the dataset and the BI tool we utilized. Then, we'll explain the technical components we employed, including the Python code we developed. Finally, we'll demonstrate the process of integrating this code into the BI tool and present the achieved outcomes.

4.1 The dataset

For this study, we used a sample of 10 registration forms for the doctoral cycle at our university. These forms were scanned in PDF format, handwritten, and filled in using two languages: Arabic and French. Intentionally, we collected information on these forms from

different individuals to test various writing styles, as depicted in the two examples shown in Figures 6 and 7.

Handwritten form for person X, titled "Fiche d'inscription en doctorat année universitaire 2019 / 2020". The form includes the following information:

- Code national de l'Étudiant de CNE: 30064483
- Numéro de la carte d'identité CIN: 271440033
- Nom: OUAZ
- Prénoms: OUBAL
- Date de naissance: 15/03/1998
- Lieu de naissance: Fesok
- Nationalité: Marocaine
- Adresse: 21, n. 2, 1st et 2nd
- Mobile: 0606348088
- E-mail: ylaouez@ymail.com
- Situation actuelle: Célibataire
- Profession: Enseignant
- Dernier diplôme obtenu: Licence Spécialité: physique Année: 2015
- Formation Doctorale choisie: 203
- Laboratoire: LARFAD

Signature de l'étudiant: [Signature] Fait à Settat le: 02/09/2023

Figure 6: Example 1 of a form handwritten by person X

Handwritten form for person Y, titled "Fiche d'inscription en doctorat année universitaire 2019 / 2020". The form includes the following information:

- Code national de l'Étudiant de CNE: 3150127
- Numéro de la carte d'identité CIN: WA158412
- Nom: ALLALI
- Prénoms: Mina
- Date de naissance: 12/10/1993
- Lieu de naissance: Berrechid
- Nationalité: Marocaine
- Adresse: 95, Bloc 6, Hay Hassani, Berrechid.
- Mobile: 06.03.15.00.92
- E-mail: ALLALIMina@gmail.com
- Situation actuelle: Célibataire
- Profession: Comptable
- Dernier diplôme obtenu: Master Spécialité: Math Année: 2012
- Formation Doctorale choisie: MAI
- Laboratoire: MAI

Signature de l'étudiant: [Signature] Fait à Settat le: 13/09/2023

Figure 7: Example 2 of a form handwritten by person Y

4.2 The BI tool

In this work, we adopted Power BI—a data visualization solution developed by Microsoft for creating dashboards and disseminating them within an enterprise [8].

The selection of Power BI was based on several criteria:

1. Tool reputation: It has consistently been ranked as a leader in Gartner's Magic Quadrant for several years [9].
2. Free availability: It includes a free desktop version, rich in features and easy to install.
3. Connector versatility: It allows data retrieval from various sources (web, databases, flat files, PDFs, Python, etc.) through its numerous connectors.

Although Power BI includes a PDF connector, distinguishing it from other tools that may not have it yet, it struggles to accurately extract data from scanned PDFs compared to printed PDFs. Our proposed solution in this work involves using the Python connector instead of the PDF connector to retrieve data from the scanned forms presented in the previous section onto the BI tool.

4.3 The technical environment

The programs we developed to address our data extraction challenge from scanned files on BI tools rely on two primary components: Handprint and AWS:

4.3.1 Handprint

Handwritten Page Recognition Test [10] is a Python command that utilizes online HTR services to recognize text in images, whether handwritten or not. It performs the following steps:

1. Downloads the image from a specific location.
2. Resizes the image if necessary.
3. Sends the image to the relevant cloud-based HTR service. The currently supported services by Handprint include Google's Cloud Vision API, Microsoft's Computer Vision API, Amazon's Textract, and Rekognition.
4. Waits for results.
5. Creates a new image annotated with the results.
6. Saves the results as JSON and text files.

Handprint is coded in Python and is compatible with various operating systems. To use it, it needs to be installed like any Python package using pipx or pip commands [10]. Once installed, it requires a copy of the file containing the identification information for the selected cloud HTR service [11] to communicate seamlessly. The cloud services we used in this work are Amazon's Textract and Rekognition. The steps for generating this file and installing Handprint will be explained in detail in the following section.

4.3.2 AWS

Amazon Web Services (AWS) is a division of the e-commerce giant Amazon, officially launched in 2006 [12]. It offers a cloud computing platform with over 200 specialized services in computing, storage, data analysis, networking, deployment, artificial intelligence, machine learning, etc. [13]. Among these services, we chose two related to our handwritten data extraction challenge:

- **Amazon Textract:** A machine learning service that automatically extracts text, whether handwritten or not, from scanned documents using five different APIs.
- **Amazon Rekognition:** Identifies objects, people, text, scenes, and more in images and videos using advanced deep learning techniques [15].

Both services are paid, but they offer free trials, which we utilized for this work. To use them, creating an account to access the AWS management console is necessary [16]. Once this step is completed, we imported the file containing the AWS identification information required for Handprint using the following procedure [17]:

1. Select "Users" in the navigation pane and choose the name of the profile we created.
2. Go to the "Security credentials" section and click on "Create access key."
3. Fill in the required information and press "Download .csv file."
4. Store the generated information in a JSON file as it is the required format by Handprint. The file we created is named "**amazoncredentials.json**" and it contains the data illustrated in Figure 8.

```
{  
  "aws_access_key_id": "AKIAWJIUGA57TAUTJ3GU",  
  "aws_secret_access_key": "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",  
  "region_name": "us-west-2"  
}
```

Figure 8: Contents of the amazoncredentials.json file

4.3.3 Handprint and AWS connection

After installing Handprint, configuring the AWS account, and creating the JSON file, two actions are needed to finalize the connection between AWS services and Handprint. Firstly, placing the generated JSON file in the "credentials" directory of Handprint, as shown in Figure 9, and secondly, executing a command in the format of "handprint -a SERVICENAME CREDENTIALSFILE.json" for each service, as demonstrated in Figure 10.

Figure 9: View of the "credentials" directory in Handprint

Figure 10: Execution results of the command for both Amazon Textract and Rekognition services

4.4 Python code

Once the installation and configuration of Handprint and AWS are completed, we developed two Python codes: The first one utilizes the Amazon Textract service, and the second one uses Amazon Rekognition, as illustrated in Figures 11 and 12.

7. Read each text file generated by Handprint after data extraction from each image format form.
8. Extract useful data for the dashboard from the text files.
9. Store the extracted data in the table initialized at the beginning of the program.

4.5 The results of the Python codes

Executing the two codes presented in the previous section on Jupyter Notebook yields the following results:

```
Out[15]:
```

	Family Name	First Name	ID Number	Laboratory	Training
0	ALLALI	Mina	WA158412	MISI	MAI
0	JAHOURI	Jihane	SE144519	MIET	MAI
0	to	ovivi	NE448676	MISI	MAI
0	HALWI	saema	CI202023	MISI	MAI
0	MASSOUDI	Kawtar	WA193386	LAMSAD	ISI
0	SALHI	Hanaue	HE141489	LAMSAD	ISI
0	about	oritis	sh149933	LAMSAD	ISI
0	SAADI	RANIA	WA194918	LAMSAD	RSI
0	ojh	5ball	WA194955	STS	PSI
0		im	WA141617	STS	ISI

Figure 13: Results of the Amazon Textract code

```
Out[42]:
```

	Family Name	First Name	ID Number	Laboratory	Training
0	ALLALI	Mina	WA158412	MIS	MAI
0	JAHOURI	Jihane	SE144519	MIET	MAI
0	زهرة	رشيدة	NE448676	UNIVERSITÉ HASSAN TERNASSAN Université Hassan TerFacul... TÉNASSAN Université Hassan TerFaculté des Sciences T...	
0	HALWI	shema	CI202023	MISI	MAI
0	MASSOUDI	Kawtar	WA193386	LAMSADSignaturedeletudiant	ISI
0	SALHI	Hanane	HE141489	LAMSAD	ISI
0	جيهان	الخلقني	1149933	UNIVERSITE HASSAN1 Université Hassan TerFac...	
0	AADI	RANIA	WA194918	LAMADSignaturedeletudiant	RSI
0	سارة	الطباري	WA194955	STS	PSI
0	الزبدى	رشيد	WA141617	STS	PSI

Figure 14: Results of the Amazon Rekognition code

As shown in Figures 13 and 14, the data extracted by the two Amazon web services are dissimilar, despite both using the same forms. This discrepancy in results will be explained in detail in the next chapter.

In addition to the retrieved data, executing the codes resulted in a set of files generated by Handprint, including annotated image files, JSON, and text files for each form, as seen in Figures 15.

Figure 15: Files generated by Handprint from a scanned form

4.6 The integration of the codes into the BI tool

After testing and validating the Python programs on Jupyter Notebook, we integrated them into Power BI using its Python connector [18]. Figures 16 and 17 show the results obtained after their executions in Power BI:

Figure 16: Results of the Python program using Amazon Textract on Power BI

Figure 17: Results of the Python program using Amazon Rekognition on Power BI

At this stage, we can confirm that the solution we have developed, as part of this work, effectively addresses our challenge of extracting handwritten data from scanned

documents using a BI tool. The next step will be to examine the accuracy of the obtained results, and that is what we will explore in the next chapter.

5. RESULTS ASSESSMENT

The objective of this chapter is to analyze the results of the implemented solution, both in terms of data and files, to compare and qualify their accuracies. Initially, we'll discuss the files generated by Handprint. Subsequently, we'll examine the data extracted by each Amazon web service to identify their advantages and drawbacks.

5.1 Handprint Results

The successful execution of Handprint commands generates three significant files:

- **An annotated image:** This is a copy of the scanned file in PNG image format containing the text recognized by the services superimposed on the initial text, as seen in the example illustrated in Figure 18.

Figure 18 : Exemple d'une image annotée générée par Handprint

- **A JSON file:** This contains the detected text along with additional attributes such as ID, type (word, line, etc.), height, width, etc.
- **A Text file:** This stores only the text recognized by the services.

The solution primarily uses Python to parse the generated text files and retrieve useful data in tabular form. However, other alternative solutions exist to fulfill the same requirement, such as:

Extracting data from the annotated image generated by Handprint using an OCR, similar to what we did in our previous article [1].

Retrieving data directly from the JSON or text file in Power BI using its connectors [19] and [20].

5.2 Amazon Textract Results

The table below summarizes the evaluation results of the data extracted by Amazon Textract:

Table 1: The advantages and disadvantages of Amazon Textract

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recognizes printed and handwritten text. - 95% accuracy in recognizing printed text characters. - 90% accuracy in recognizing handwritten text characters. - Maintains spaces. - Differentiates between uppercase and lowercase letters. - Recognizes numbers. - Recognizes symbols (e.g., comma, /, etc.). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does not recognize Arabic writing. - Occasionally fails to recognize symbols like @, periods, commas, etc., in handwritten text. - Sometimes fails to recognize accents in handwritten text. - Misinterprets certain letters (e.g., substitutes 'i' for) due to poor handwriting. - Fails to extract letters correctly from printed text (e.g., 'nationa' instead of 'national'), possibly due to scan quality.

5.3 Amazon Rekognition Results

Similarly, we evaluated the data extracted by Amazon Rekognition and compiled the advantages and disadvantages of this service in the table below:

Table 2: The advantages and disadvantages of Amazon Rekognition

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recognizes printed and handwritten text. - Recognizes Arabic writing. - 80% accuracy in recognizing printed text characters. - 70% accuracy in recognizing handwritten text characters. - Differentiates between uppercase and lowercase letters. - Recognizes numbers. - Recognizes symbols (e.g., comma, /, etc.). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Occasionally fails to recognize symbols like @, periods, commas, etc., in handwritten text. - Sometimes fails to recognize accents in both printed and handwritten text. - Misinterprets certain letters (e.g., substitutes 'e' for)) due to poor handwriting. - Fails to extract letters correctly from printed text (e.g., 'nationa' instead of 'national'), possibly due to scan quality. - Occasionally removes spaces between words in printed and handwritten text. - Sometimes adds significant spaces between characters in handwritten text. - Fails to translate entire phrases from printed and handwritten text. - Has inconsistent character recognition: Multiple runs of the service on the same form yield different results each time.

6. CONCLUSION

On this manuscript, we have successfully addressed the issue of data extraction from scanned and handwritten files onto BI tools by proposing a solution that leverages artificial intelligence techniques and languages.

Overall, the results from the two web services we used are satisfactory as they enable recognition of over 70% of the characters present in the files, whether they are printed or handwritten. For improved results, we suggest combining both web services.

Firstly, utilizing Amazon Textract for manual data extraction due to its higher precision (recognizing 90% of handwritten text characters accurately). Then, complementing the undetected data from Textract by running Amazon Rekognition, especially for interpreting data in other languages such as Arabic.

Lastly, it's important to note that both Amazon web services are paid, but this should not pose an obstacle at an enterprise scale.

References

- 1) Sara EL HABBARI, M'hamed-amine SOUMIAA, Mohamed MANSOURI, « OPTICAL CHARACTER RECOGNITION APPLIED ON BUSINESSINTELLIGENCE TOOLS », in Jilin Daxue Xuebao (Gongxueban)/Journal of Jilin University (Engineering and Technology Edition), Vol: 58 Issue: 08-2021.
- 2) <https://www.memoireonline.com/09/09/2694/Systeme-de-reconnaissance-hors-ligne-des-mots-manuscrits-arabe-pour-multi-scripteurs.html>
- 3) <https://www.ibm.com/fr-fr/topics/deep-learning>
- 4) Khalkar, Rohini & Dikhit, Adarsh & Goel, Anirudh. (2021). Handwritten Text Recognition using Deep Learning (CNN & RNN). IARJSET. 8. 870-881. 10.17148/IARJSET.2021.86148.
- 5) Kumar, Munish & Gupta, Surbhi & Garg, Anupam. (2019). Improved Object Recognition Results Using SIFT and ORB Feature Detector. Multimedia Tools and Applications. 78. 10.1007/s11042-019-08232-6.
- 6) Laëtitia Rousseau, Eric Anquetil, Jean Camillerapp. Reconnaissance de l'écriture manuscrite hors-ligne par reconstruction de l'ordre du tracé. MajecSTIC 2005 : Manifestation des Jeunes Chercheurs francophones dans les domaines des STIC, IRISA – IETR – LTSI, Nov 2005, Rennes, France. pp.401-404. (inria-00000740)
- 7) Rosyda, Salma & Purboyo, Tito. (2018). A Review of Various Handwriting Recognition Methods.
- 8) <https://powerbi.microsoft.com/fr-fr/>
- 9) <https://powerbi.microsoft.com/en-my/blog/microsoft-named-a-leader-in-the-2023-gartner-magic-quadrant-for-analytics-and-bi-platforms/>
- 10) <https://pypi.org/project/handprint/>
- 11) <https://caltechlibrary.github.io/handprint/configuration.html>
- 12) https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Amazon_Web_Services
- 13) <https://aws.amazon.com/fr/what-is-aws/>
- 14) <https://aws.amazon.com/fr/textract/pricing/>

- 15) <https://us-east-1.console.aws.amazon.com/rekognition/home?region=us-east-1#/>
- 16) https://docs.aws.amazon.com/fr_fr/signin/latest/userguide/console-sign-in-tutorials.html
- 17) <https://github.com/caltechlibrary/handprint/wiki/Creating-credentials-for-use-with-Amazon-Rekognition-and-Texttract>
- 18) <https://learn.microsoft.com/fr-fr/power-bi/connect-data/desktop-python-scripts>
- 19) <https://learn.microsoft.com/fr-fr/power-query/connectors/json>
- 20) <https://learn.microsoft.com/fr-fr/power-query/connectors/text-csv>